

In Vitro Embryo Production In Bovines

Prachi Sharma

Department of Veterinary Gynaecology and Obstetrics
College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, Anand, Gujarat, 388001

Abstract

In vitro procedures (IVP) are being used commercially in conjunction with embryo transfer (ET) in several countries. Genetic improvement is a common goal that researchers are working on and is an outcome desired by all cattle owners. In Vitro Embryo Production is one such tool that can help in achieving this goal at a faster pace. This article aims to briefly introduce and describe the In vitro embryo production technology to its readers for a better understanding of the technology.

Key Words: In Vitro Embryo Production, IVF, OPU, IVC, Fertilization

Introduction

A range of instruments often referred to as assisted reproductive technologies have been created as a result of the scientific and technical advancements made in animal reproduction over the past several decades (ART). These techniques' main objectives are to increase the number of offspring from genetically better animals and spread germplasm around the globe. In vitro embryogenesis is a relatively contemporary method of assisted reproduction. Oocytes from donor animals are taken out, developed, and fertilized in vitro in this process. The resulting embryos are either cryopreserved for eventual transfer or directly transplanted to patients before being grown in the lab. By repeatedly collecting several oocytes from a single cow using a process termed transvaginal ultrasound-guided oocyte recovery, the requirement to maintain large numbers of purebred cows of the dam breed can be significantly reduced. Today's most significant developments in IVP aim to boost efficiency across

each stage, including ovarian stimulation, oocyte recovery, maturation, fertilization, embryo development, freezing, transfer, and pregnancy establishment.

Ovarian Treatment and Oocyte Recovery

Oocytes for IVP can be obtained by: (1) ultrasound-guided follicular aspiration from live animals or by ovariectomy and (2) post-mortem follicular aspiration (abattoir-derived ovaries). In both scenarios, oocytes are aspirated from a heterogeneous pool of antral follicles, 2 to 8 mm in size, including both non-ovulatory and ovulatory follicular waves and dominant and subordinate follicles in these waves. Oocytes in the large dominant follicles will be in the so-called pre-maturation or capacitation process, building up their competence for final maturation, fertilization, and sustaining embryonic development. In the case of follicle aspiration, it is possible to obtain four to five usable oocytes per donor session while stimulation by FSH can increase oocyte recovery rates to 20 per donor session. The strategies to improve the number of follicles and oocyte quality include (1) donor stimulation with gonadotropins, (2) partial in vivo pre-maturation, termed 'coasting', and (3) dietary supplementation with energy concentrates rich in fatty acids.

Oocyte Maturation

The growing gamete experiences both nuclear and cytoplasmic alterations during oocyte maturation. The process of meiosis from the prophase during the first meiotic division to the metaphase of the second meiotic division (MII) at the time of ovulation is referred to as nuclear oocyte maturation. Along with nuclear maturation, the oocyte undergoes several modifications that result in alterations to its organelles, proteins, and transcripts. Meiosis halts at MII until fertilization, at which point it starts up again and finishes separating the second polar body. Oocytes will typically reach MII nuclear maturity under in vitro circumstances within 20 to 24 hours, at which point they will be prepared for fertilization. Due to poor cytoplasmic oocyte maturation, the diverse source of aspirated immature oocytes from ovarian follicles at various stages of follicular growth may undermine developmental competence. Under ideal circumstances, between 85% and 90% of cultivated immature oocytes will attain MII after IVM. Although this success rate may be considered good, oocyte cytoplasmic maturation and complete acquisition of developmental competence frequently do not follow nuclear maturation and may be a contributing cause of deficits in fertilization and/or development. Oocytes that develop in vivo produce more blastocysts than their IVM counterparts in this aspect.

Fertilization

Oocytes and spermatozoa are co-incubated with one another for up to 18 to 24 hours during IVF once IVM is finished. When there are few OPU donor oocytes present, the microenvironment in the fertilization dish is 50 to 100 l; when there are many slaughterhouses mass-collected oocytes present, the milieu is often greater than 400 l. Typically, dead spermatozoa, seminal plasma, debris, and freezing media are removed from the spermatozoa and the more motile fraction is chosen using swim-up or density gradient centrifugation techniques.

In Vitro Culture (IVC)

The fertilized eggs undergo IVC for 7 days following IVF until they reach the blastocyst stage. Typically, 20–40% of cultivated putative zygotes will develop into blastocysts. When embryos reach the blastocyst stage, they can either be cryopreserved or transferred using similar techniques to those used for in vivo blastocysts. To attain greater post-thaw viability results overall, which can aid in boosting pregnancy rates in the event of direct embryo transfer methods, only high-quality IVP embryos are advised for cryopreservation. Even though slow freezing is becoming more common. The highest pregnancy rates are achieved by choosing the "best" or most viable embryos that can withstand the cryopreservation procedure for direct transfer, according to new trends. Individual embryo oxygen consumption rate, major substrate metabolite intake absorption analysis (including pyruvate, glucose, and amino acids), and generation of metabolites via cellular metabolism (such as lactate) might all be held up as gold standards. The comparatively low rates of embryonic growth to the blastocyst stage are concerning given the high maturation and cleavage rates attained.

Conclusion

Over the past 40 years, in vitro fertilization (IVF) has gained acceptance as a reproductive technique. Despite a few justifiable drawbacks, the procedure's success is mostly a result of the various reproductive benefits it offers, which enable livestock owners to effectively increase the genetic diversity of their herds. The capacity to generate more calves faster with IVF is one of its most well-liked advantages. No hormonal therapy is required, and pregnant donors can also undergo ovum pick-up furthermore, it can be carried out on young heifers or prepubertal calves. IVF requires less semen than traditional AI or ET because the oocytes are housed on small plates during the fertilization procedure. This presents a plethora of opportunities. Depending on the quality, one straw of conventional semen can fertilize up to 15 donors' oocytes. Breeders can maximize the value of expensive or uncommon semen by in vitro embryo production.

